

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

5th TNA Call Documentation – User Report (User)

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

After the StoRIES Transnational Access stay or Virtual Access, users are required to submit a *User Report*. This should be done within 4 weeks after the Access is completed unless otherwise agreed. The *User Report* will be given to the User(s) by the Project Management. The report contains sections related to the work performed, the main results and observations that were achieved.

This document should be completed, signed, and sent to the following person, along with the *TNA Cost Claim Form* and all eligible receipts either by e-mail [REDACTED]

Summary questionnaire for users who have been granted Transnational Access (TNA) under the StoRIES project Horizon 2020 TNA scheme. More information on StoRIES TNA can be found in “[General Rules](#)” and in “[Access Policy](#)” which can be found on the StoRIES webpage.

General information about the project

Project title (as used in application)	Safe Uncertainty Reduction in Expansion for Thermal Energy Storage
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	SURE-TES
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	CIC energigUNE, Thermal Loops (TES)
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Packed bed TES, alternating thermo-mechanical stress, tank expansion, thermal ratcheting, failure modes, sensor technology, decarbonization of industrial processes
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	7.10.2024
Departure date (from town where RI located)	26.10.2024
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	8.10.2024
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	24.10.2024
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	2
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	RI not working
Number of days using the RI	15
Number of users granted access (group size)	2
Comments	[REDACTED] was taking part in the access until 10.10.2024

User	
User group leader or sole applicant (user group member 1)	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	Fraunhofer ISE
Country of Employer	Germany
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 2	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	Fraunhofer ISE
Country of Employer	Germany
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 3	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
User group member 4	
First name	
Last name	
Affiliation / Employer	
Country of Employer	
E-mail	
Comments	
Please insert more fields if your groups had more than four members.	

Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results

Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)

[Please describe short the main objectives of your project]

Cyclic thermal loading of confined granular beds in TES (thermal energy storage) vessels induces alternating thermal and mechanical stresses in the storage material and in the tank walls. This phenomenon and its consequences have been described as 'thermal ratcheting', and in many cases of TES prototypes it has led to severe damage to the systems after a few hundred charge and discharge cycles.

As this mechanism has not yet been often and thoroughly studied experimentally, the objective of our project was to advance reliable in-situ measurement capabilities for the thermal ratcheting effect, and perform first tests of the developed measurement system under real working conditions of the slag based TES storage system at the CIC energiGUNE.

Our goal was to gain hands-on expertise on setting up the developed measurement system for thermal ratcheting and connecting it to the existing thermal storage tank. From this experience, as well as from the measurement data of the following charge-discharge experiments, we expected benefits for the validation and enhancement of the measurement system.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

[Please summarise the work carried you (steps taken, instrumentation used, techniques employed, data sources consulted etc.)]

The following tasks were executed during the access:

Week 1:

- Detailed planning of the geometry of the measurement setup and the interfaces to the tank
- Design of suitable experiments and boundary conditions, respecting the expected sensor performance and constraints of the facility
- Preparation of the tank for the distance sensor connections (remove insulation at 8 positions, cut threads)
- Setting up the measurement support structure (2x2x3 m³) around the tank (Figure 1).
- Fine adjustment of the support structure in relation to the tank geometry
- Installation of the water cooling and thermal insulation for the support structure (Figure 2)

Week 2:

- Installation of 8 LVDT distance sensors with custom measurement tips (in 4 opposite measurement pairs) (Figure 3)
- Installation of 1 optical laser triangulation sensor and sensor air cooling system
- Installation of 12 Thermocouples for
 - cooling water (2)
 - support structure (5)
 - ambient air (3)
 - tank surface (1)
 - triangulation sensor cooling (1)

- Connection of sensor electronics
- Setting up data acquisition system (Multiplexer + Industrial PC)
- Thermocouple temperature calibration
- Cold test measurement
- Warm test measurement (120 °C)
- Drift test measurement over night

16.10.24: Completion of the measurement system and pretesting, ready for hot tests.

17.10. - 24.10.24:

- Measurement of six charge-discharge cycles (each one 8 hours charging to 550°C and 16 hours discharge with ambient air)
- Supervision of the tests, adaption of test parameters, real-time analysis of measurement data
- Monitoring and correlation with the sensor equipment of the facility (45 thermocouples in the tank, thermocouples in the piping, flow rate, pressures)

24.10.+25.10.24:

- Packing of the sensitive equipment, disassembly of the mounting structure
- Joint evaluation, interpretation and discussion of the results

Figure 1: Sensor support structure during mounting around the cylindrical TES tank. The water cooling and the insulation are still missing.

Figure 2: Finished temperature-stabilized sensor support structure for 8 distance sensors at the steel tank surface.

Figure 3: Distance sensor system with temperature stable measurement tip going through the tank insulation.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

[Summarise the (initial) outcomes of your study at the RI(s).]

The goal of our study was to adapt and test a measurement system for the thermal ratcheting effect on a packed bed storage tank.

Therefore, the outcomes of our study can be divided into

- 1) findings which relate to the setup, performance, and improvements of our measurement system,
- 2) and the actual measurement data from the CIC thermal loop (distance measurements and operational data of the tank) which have been collected with the measurement system.

1) measurement structure

Our study at the RI was the first application of our measurement system, after the controlled calibration tests of the LVDT sensors in our lab. Therefore it was not clear how the system would perform under external influences, mainly strong temperature variations and vibrations.

During the tests with increased thermal radiation levels and changes in the ambient temperature of up to 10 K, we have seen that – despite water cooling – the temperatures in the relevant parts of the support structure (horizontal bars) fluctuate up to 1.0 K. In the parts with minor relevance (vertical profiles), the fluctuations are up to 2.5 K. Nevertheless, the thermal behaviour of the structure was reproducible and did not significantly affect the possibility of determining tank size changes of several μm .

The *repeatability* of a single tank size measurement with the used support structure, temperature stabilization and sensor equipment under the boundary conditions during the experiments was found to be less than 2-30 μm . The high uncertainty on this value results from the fact that the 'true' behaviour of the tank is unknown, which means that we can make the 'worst case' assumption that during one cycle, the tank did not change at all in its size, and that the measured size change is fully caused by measurement errors.

2) measurement data of the packed bed storage

After installation of all sensors and an initial overnight drift measurement (overall change of 3 μm , with temporary spikes of 10 μm), the thermal loop at the facility was put into operation. The packed bed tank was charged with 550 °C inlet temperature and discharged at room temperature. Six charge-discharge cycles were performed. During all measurements, the size of the tank was measured with the distance sensors (Figure 4).

As expected, the size change of the tank of around 5000 μm due to thermal expansion with the temperature is clearly visible. Unexpectedly, also several mm of lateral movement of the tank occurred, most probably due to the thermal expansion and force transmission of an air supply pipe. This caused several sensors to leave their valid measurement range (2-10 V) during the charged state of the tank. But no damage was caused to the sensors, and as the objective of the measurement was to compare the size of the tank in cold state, this effect did not negatively impact the results.

Even though the diameter increase of the tank between cold and hot state was more than 4000 μm , and there was an additional lateral movement of several 1000 μm , after each cycle the measurement values went almost back to their initial state, with almost all observed differences less than 20-30 μm . These very low values could be considered measurement errors of the system or thermal ratcheting effect of the tank – see next section.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

[Discuss the data obtained and describe the major scientific conclusions drawn.]

1) measurement structure

During the above-described tests, we have learnt the following concerning our measurement system:

- we can quantify the sensitivity of the measurement system to external influences (room temperature, outside temperature, people in the laboratory, draughts, vibrations from work, heat input from tank at 550°C). Even though some of the influences can cause errors in the same magnitude as the expected small measurement signal (a few μm per cycle), these effects did not make reliable measurements impossible, and we were able to apply corrections to most of the influences.
- Our measurement structure could be flexibly adapted to the tank without losing its function.
- We did not observe a significant difference between the two kinds of tested low-expansion measuring tips (metal / glass).
- There was no significant difference in performance between the two used LVDT sensor types (μ -epsilon DTA-5D and LDR-10-CA).
- LVDT and laser triangulation measurement (at one measurement point at the lower part of the tank up to 140 °C) were consistent.

The following aspects were identified as improvement possibilities, to decrease the measurement errors:

- Use a higher measurement range of the LVDT sensors
- Improve the temperature and radiation shielding of the structure and the sensors
- Increase the cooling water stability (use additional pump for more flow rate)

- Increase the mechanical stability of the support structure (add diagonal profiles in addition to horizontal ones)
- Make possibility for better fine-adjustment of the sensor positions, in order to make test measurements and then readjust when it is clear how the tank moves

2) measurement data of the packed bed storage

Figure 5 shows the measured size change for each of the six cycles. The values were calculated from the data for the four sensor pairs shown in Figure 4. Due to the high variation of the tank size during one cycle, the statistical uncertainty on the size differences is still relatively high (5-15 μm , depending on measurement conditions). Nevertheless, it is a very good sign that all measurements are very close to 0 μm size change, which means there were no large measurement errors present.

The mayor source of the uncertainty on the size change is most probably the tank temperature during the size measurement. Considering the thermal expansion of steel, there is a size change in the order of 10 $\mu\text{m}/\text{K}$. As an indication, the temperatures measured with the thermocouple closest to the distance sensors are shown. It is clear that the temperature fluctuations of a few K may be the reason for the mayor part of the observed size changes per cycle.

But for a first understanding and quantification of the thermal ratcheting effect, it is not necessary to measure individual size changes of separate cycles. It can be sufficient to quantify the total size increase during several measurements, to obtain a 'mean' size increase per cycle. By doing so (right points of Figure 5), we see that the sensor pair 3-4 indicates a significant non-zero size increase of $89 \pm 20 \mu\text{m}$. For six cycles, this corresponds to $15 \pm 3 \mu\text{m}$ size increase per cycle. The other three sensor pairs do not show a significant size change within their uncertainty intervals of 20-30 μm .

This result is interesting, because due to the mechanical structure of the tank, one would expect the largest buckling effect due to forces exerted from the filler material in the middle of the tank, at sensor pairs 3-4 and 7-8. Yet it is not clear why only one of those sensor pairs was detecting an expansion.

Based on the available data, we cannot decide with certainty whether these observations are actually a case of thermal ratcheting, occurring at the centre of the packed bed tank, or if they are caused by fluctuations, mainly due to the slightly different tank wall temperatures during the measurements. To decrease the uncertainty, the conduction of longer tests and more cycles would be necessary.

Figure 5: Top: Data derived from Figure 4: Measured size change of the packed bed thermal storage during six heating and cooling cycles. The last point on the right side shows the size difference between the first and the last cycle. Three sensor pairs are not significantly different from zero, but the middle sensor pair shows an indication of an overall tank size increase during the six cycles.

Bottom: Packed bed temperatures measured with the thermocouples closest to the sensor pair. The slight variations of around 1-2 K before and after each cycle would cause a thermal extension effect with the same magnitude as the measured size changes. This is the major source of statistical measurement errors and can therefore be decreased with increasing the number of measurements.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

[Describe the main achievements during your stay at the site(s)]

During our stay, we successfully set up and tested a measurement system for thermal ratcheting. Using a custom-made water-cooled support structure and LVDT distance sensors, we demonstrated that size measurements of a packed-bed tank with the desired measurement accuracy could be achieved. The repeatability of the measurement system is excellent, and we were reaching values below 10-20 μm , corresponding to 12–24 ppm relative to the tank size.

This is not yet sufficient for the highly significant detection of thermal ratcheting during a few cycles (less than 5 ppm uncertainty would be desirable), but based on our results we expect that the thermal ratcheting effect can be detected with the used measurement system during longer measurements, which would reduce the relative impact of sources of constant measurement errors.

Building on these findings, we can now confidently expect that the improved measurement system will be appropriate for a new, rectangular packed-bed test tank which is now being constructed in Freiburg. This setup will enable long-term experiments with enhanced measurement accuracy, targeting at least 100 cycles over a 3-month period.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

[List problems and issues you had, completing out your research project: Did you get access to all the necessary equipment, facilities, databases, etc.?

If not, please specify the problems that occurred and list equipment that was not working or accessible.]

The backing from the CIC staff regarding facilities and database access was outstanding. Their support in setting up and dismantling the measurement structure and in the laborious installing of all sensors and the DAQ system is greatly appreciated. Integration of the sensor system to the existing facilities worked flawlessly due to the excellent communication and coordination prior to the access.

One minor issue was that our measurement system was not fully able to compensate the fast temperature fluctuations (5-8 K) in the laboratory environment, which were primarily caused by switching the electric heater (100 kW), but also from varying ambient weather/temperature conditions. A major part of the uncertainty on the acquired measurement values is attributed to the temperature fluctuations.

This is an improvement opportunity for us to make our measurement system more independent of ambient air temperatures for the next measurements.

Intended publications

[Explain where and how you expect to publish the outcomes of your project work. Include also anything already published (What and where?)]

Based on the final evaluation and a joint critical assessment of the reliability of the measurement data and conclusions, we are planning a conference contribution.

Data management

[Describe the further usage and storage of project data]

All collected measurement data is currently stored on Fraunhofer ISE servers for further, in-depth analysis. With agreement of the CIC, we welcome collaboration and are open to sharing data with researchers who have an academic or research-based interest in utilizing it.

Conclusions / additional comments

[Provide any other comments you might have on your work]

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>					
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify any problems]</i>					
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify]</i>					
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				

<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i> There is always a possibility that researchers may be harmed in the lab, working with large structures and high temperatures. But the safety regulations and measures were appropriate, and no harm was caused.											
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
<i>[Please provide details]</i>											
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>							
<i>[Comment]</i>											
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
<i>[Please provide suggestions for specific type of facilities missing (RI gaps) or measurement / experiments you would like to perform which cannot be done on current StoRIES facilities]</i>											

Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.

[Your suggestions]

Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support

Awareness Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES.
 Yes No

[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]

Personal experience Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support?
 Yes No

[Please provide details]

Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Please provide details]

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.

I have read the [StoRIES privacy policy](#) for participation in the StoRIES TNA and consent to participation and the associated data processing.

Date of submission to StoRIES TNA team: 16/12/2024

Your full name: [Redacted]

Your signature: [Redacted]

